

6G-SANDBOX

Supporting Architectural and technological
Network evolutions through an intelligent, secured
and twinning enabled Open eXperimentation
facility

Deliverable D3.1

Open API design and implementation for the
6G-SANDBOX Library

Date: 31/12/2023

Version: 1.0

Grant Agreement	101096328
Document number	D3.1
Document title	Open API design and implementation for the 6G-SANDBOX Library
Lead Beneficiary	TID
Editor(s)	David Artuñedo Guillén (TEL)
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Dissemination level	Public
Contractual date of delivery	31/12/2023
Status	Final
Version	1.0
File name	6G-SANDBOX_D3.1_v1.0.pdf

Document History

Version

V0.1	Table of Contents
V0.9	Draft version for Review
V1.0	Final version

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ABSTRACT

The main scope of this document is to report the design and implementation activities conducted towards realising the openness approach of the 6G-SANDBOX, an approach that enables the abstraction of network and experimentation capabilities, allowing for the creation of Trial Networks. As Trial Network we define a fully configurable, manageable, and controllable network which may composed of virtual and/or physical elements, and it can support experimentation services, such as technology validations and measurement campaigns. The 6G-SANDBOX approach for the Trial Networks is built upon two main principles, namely a) the use of open and standardised APIs (based on the 3GPP Common API Framework - CAPIF) for exposing the capabilities of each of the Trial Network elements, and b) the hosting of Trial Network software components in a common repository, called in the project framework as 6G Library, which eases an experimenter to perform a modular and automatic deployment of a Trial Network by selecting on demand the required elements from the library.

KEYWORDS

Common API Framework, Trial Network, 6G library

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 DOCUMENT STRUCTURE

The core part of the document is divided into the following sections:

- Section 2 “Open API Design” offers a description of the 6G Library concept, and the way it has been materialized upon the concept of 6G Library Objects. It also provides background information on the API framework that the project adopts.
- Section 3 “The 6G SANDBOX Open API framework” provides a detailed description of the architecture and the functionalities of the API framework that the project adopts, i.e., the 3GPP CAPIF.
- Section 4 “CAPIF deployment and expansion activities” explains the activities conducted for deploying the core function of CAPIF in a Kubernetes cluster as well as the development activities for an auxiliary tool for CAPIF management.
- Section 5 “CAPIF integration into 6G Library” contains a detailed description of the activities towards integrating CAPIF into the 6G Library, as it is a fundamental element/object for the composition of any Trial Network.
- Section 6 “CAPIF Lifecycle” contains operational aspects of CAPIF, splitting the operation into Day 0/Day 1 /Day 2+ which is an industry standard way to approach lifecycle descriptions.

At the end of the document, section 7 outlines the conclusions on the defined strategy for Open APIs in 6G-SANDBOX and the References are listed.

1.2 TARGET AUDIENCE

The release of the deliverable is public, intending to expose the overall 6G-SANDBOX facility to a wide variety of research individuals and communities. From specific to broader, different target audiences for D3.1 are identified as detailed below:

- The Project Consortium to validate that all objectives and proposed technological advancements have been analysed and to ensure that, through the identified requirements (functional and non-functional), the next actions can be concretely derived. Furthermore, the deliverable sets to establish a common understanding among the Consortium with regards to: i) the Facility architecture to be set for reference, and ii) the technologies to be utilised, deployed and extended per platform.
- The Research Community and funding EC Organisation to: i) summarise the 6G-SANDBOX scope, objectives and intended project innovations, ii) detail the 6G-SANDBOX Facility and the four platforms as well as the targeted use cases that shall be demonstrated and measure provided technological advancements, and iii) present the related requirements and associated KPIs that must be tackled to achieve the expected results.
- The vertical actors that will be engaged to the project with the process of the open calls and will utilise the 6G-SANDBOX facility to conduct their experiments.
- The general public for obtaining a better understanding of the framework and scope of the 6G-SANDBOX project.

2 OPEN API DESIGN

This section starts with the description of the Trial Network concept, since this concept shapes all the technical activities in 6G-SANDBOX, including the design of the Open API strategy. Trial Networks are created from 6G Library objects, thus, a description of the 6G Library is provided as well. Next, we investigate how 3GPP tackles Network Openness and API management, as an effort to highlight the origin of our Open API approach.

2.1 TRIAL NETWORK CONCEPT

A Trial Network is defined as a fully configurable, manageable, and controllable network which may composed of virtual and/or physical elements, and it can support experimentation services, such as technology validations and measurement campaigns. Fundamental step for the creation of a Trial Network is the abstraction of network-, service- and experimentation- specific components, in a sense that they can be hosted in a library as individual elements/objects ready to be selected and combined on-demand. The abstraction refers to an extensive description of the component capabilities (i.e., possible configuration parameters, available interfaces with other components, etc.), and the procedure (in an automatable manner) for deploying, making accessible or configuring the component needs to be specified. The definition of specific details and procedures as isolated entities within the 6G Library facilitates the independent evolution of each component that may be part of a Trial Network. Additionally, this design simplifies the incorporation of new components as they become available.

Figure 1: The Trial Network Concept from the implementation perspective

Given the above-mentioned abstraction the Trial Network Lifecycle Manager (TNLCM) - introduced as the heart of the 6G-SANDBOX architecture in D2.1, enables any third party entity to set up its own Trial Network by reserving for a certain amount of time a sub-set of the actual resources available in a compute and connect infrastructure (such as the Malaga, Athens, Berlin, and Oulu experimentation platforms) and conduct experiments totally isolated from other Trial Networks running on top of the same compute and connect infrastructure. Based on the flexibility provided by the on-demand selection of elements for building a Trial Network, different requirements coming from individual experimenters or large consortiums of multiple companies, can be supported. For example, a Trial Network may be short-lived, existing only during the execution of a single experiment, or persist for month or years, giving support for multiple Experimenters and use cases coming from other research and investigation projects.

2.2 6G LIBRARY

The Trial Network software components are hosted in a common repository, called in the project framework as 6G Library, which eases an experimenter to perform a modular and automatic deployment of a Trial Network by selecting on demand the required elements from the library. Here we provide fundamental aspects of the 6G Library, such as the main tools used and the file structure used for storing an object in the library.

2.2.1 ADD AN OBJECT TO 6G LIBRARY

The objects of the 6G library should be curated and designed to serve as the foundational building blocks for constructing the Trial Network experiment. Github serves as a sophisticated version control system essential for monitoring changes within computer files, primarily employed in managing source code during software development. Its core functionalities are designed to facilitate seamless collaboration and efficient tracking of modifications made to source code files. Alterations made to the source code are tracked thus enabling users to review and revert to any previous point in the repository's history. This feature empowers developers to navigate through the development process with flexibility and precision. Github also fosters collaborative work environments by accommodating multiple developers concurrently. It achieves this by supporting non-linear development through an extensive network of parallel branches, allowing teams to work on different aspects of the project simultaneously without interference. Widely adopted across industries, Git has become a standard tool integrated into various automation systems. Its versatility and widespread usage make it a cornerstone in modern software development practices.

Moreover, the concept of 'Everything as Code (EaC)' has gained prominence in software development and DevOps methodologies. EaC involves utilizing code to define and manage IT resources, encompassing principles such as Infrastructure as Code and Config as Code. This approach leverages the advantages of Git and EaC, thereby enhancing efficiency and scalability in software development. Each element within this library embodies the EaC philosophy, designed as self-contained units equipped with the necessary automations and scripts for deployment within the 6G-SANDBOX platform.

To ensure uniformity across component creation and seamless integration, a set of predefined requirements and best practices has been established. The architectural blueprint of each component has been meticulously crafted with a focus on simplicity, clarity, versatility, scalability, and adaptability. Two fundamental aspects stand as cornerstones for every object in the library:

- Use of a predefined toolset
- Adopt a common folder structure

2.2.2 6G LIBRARY TOOLSET

The selected suite of tools shown in Figure 1 serves to automate the creation and configuration of each component, ensuring a seamless development and deployment process.

Figure 2: Toolset selected for 6G Library implementation

- **Terraform:** This tool facilitates the creation of virtual infrastructure across private cloud providers, enabling the setup of virtual networks, machines, containers, Kubernetes clusters, and more. Terraform streamlines the infrastructure provisioning process.

- **Ansible:** Employed for comprehensive component configuration, equipment setup, and integrations, Ansible enables fine-grained actions on Trial Network components. Its idempotent nature ensures reliability in configurations.
- **Jenkins:** This tool serves as the orchestrator for deploying components, executing deployment processes efficiently. Jenkins streamlines and automates deployment workflows.
- **Bash:** Enabling scripting for standalone operations, Bash provides flexibility and customization in executing various operational tasks.

2.2.3 FOLDER STRUCTURE

The folder tree representing a 6G Library Object is presented in Figure 2. Three main folders are used, namely the private, the public and the documentation folder.

Figure 3: 6G Library Object Structure

Public Folder

This folder contains the component public information that could be used by third parties to integrate the catalogue.

- **description.yaml** (file): Is a descriptor file with the component public information. It contains metadata (component name, version, etc., ...) and the public variables that should be used to deploy it.
- **changelog.yaml** (file): Is a file with the component historical evolution: new version, bug fixing, etc.

Private Folder

This folder contains the component private files with information and automation that will be used to deploy the component in a 6G-SANDBOX site.

- **values.yaml** (file): Contains variables needed by automation tools to accomplish deployment and configuration
- **manifest.yaml** (file): Contains the flow that must be followed to deploy the component

- **cloud_provider(folder)**: One folder per cloud provider where the component will be available
 - **cac (folder)**: Contains files related to configuration automation
 - **pre(folder)**: Contains files related to configuration that should be done in advance. For example, gather some information from cloud provider.
 - **install(folder)**: Contains files related to component configuration
 - **post(folder)**: Contains files related to configuration that should be done after component set-up. For example, test execution.
 - **iac (folder)**: Contains files related to infrastructure definition

Documentation Folder

It contains detailed information about the component in Markdown editor format, to enable direct integration between third parties and the catalogue.

2.3 APIS MANAGEMENT IN 3GPP NETWORKS

During the last decades, the use of Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) has served as a bridge between mobile operators and start-ups in emerging markets. Operators have begun to consider whether to open their APIs, starting from APIs related to mobile messaging, operator billing, etc. In addition, the recently witnessed convergence of IT and Telecom worlds has contributed a lot to putting APIs in the epicentre of network programming and service provisioning. Representative examples that prove this statement are: the 5G Service Based Architecture (SBA), which has been designed based on the flexibility that HTTP/2 Restful APIs to provide interaction among 3GPP network functions; the intense work on API specification and development in open project and for a (e.g., the openAPI project of TM Forum); and the wide adoption of the microservice software pattern/architecture which is based on API interacting software pieces. In this context, the management of API interactions is becoming a fundamental operation in the field of mobile networks and services.

In a complex system where various services communicate and collaborate, employing a common API framework becomes indispensable. Firstly, it fosters seamless integration and interoperability among disparate APIs. By providing a unified entry point for different services, the common API framework streamlines communication and standardizes data formats, eliminating the need for developers to navigate through the idiosyncrasies of each individual API. This not only simplifies the development process but also accelerates time-to-market for new features and services.

Secondly, a common API framework enhances security and control. Acting as a centralized control point, it can enforce authentication, authorization, and other security policies consistently across all APIs. This ensures that sensitive data is handled uniformly and mitigates the risk of vulnerabilities. Additionally, it facilitates monitoring and analytics, offering insights into API usage, performance, and potential issues. This centralized management approach enhances overall system reliability and enables organizations to adapt swiftly to changing requirements, all while maintaining a secure and efficient API ecosystem.

Especially, in the context of 3GPP networks, specifications for a common API framework (CAPIF) have been released. CAPIF includes common aspects applicable to any northbound service APIs. As such, it is a complete 3GPP API framework that covers interaction functionality among API providers and API invokers. Such functionality includes on-board and off-board of API invokers, register and release of APIs that need to be exposed by a provider, discovering of APIs by third entities, as well as authorization and authentication. CAPIF functionality is considered as one of the cornerstones in the realization of mobile network openness since it allows secure exposure of network core APIs to third party domains and enables third parties to define and expose their own APIs.

Indeed, CAPIF has already become a fundamental feature for the 3GPP SA6, targeting the interaction of various Vertical Industries with the 5G system, including Unmanned Aerial Systems, Edge Applications, Factories of the Future, V2X services, etc. The full list of the frameworks described by SA6 WG is as follows:

- CAPIF: *Common API Framework to aid 3rd party applications access to 3GPP functions.*
- SEAL: *5G Service Platform enabling common capabilities for quicker onboarding of new Verticals*
- VEAL: *Application support layer for vertical applications (V2X, UAS, FF)*

- EDGEAPP: Enables deployment of Edge Apps in compliance with 3GPP System for low latency and increased performance

Figure 4: SA WG6 API Frameworks

Beyond its initial purpose, CAPIF can be considered as a standardized API manager that can facilitate any API-based interaction, including for instance federation activities among testbeds and experimentation platforms, east-west interaction among business and orchestration layers, or exposure capabilities that reside at the edge domain (e.g., MEC APIs exposure).

One of the cornerstones in the 6G-SANDBOX approach is the capability to provide a secure, interoperable, and easy to apply API interaction with the 6G-SANDBOX architectural layers as well as with any component that is brought from externals (e.g., through open calls). To achieve this, the implementation of CAPIF specifications has been decided, based on the initial implementation from TEL and FOGUS. The implementation details and the foreseen extensions are provided in Section 3.

3 THE 6G-SANDBOX OPEN API FRAMEWORK

Considering that Trial Networks need to expose APIs to 6G-SANDBOX users, we have selected CAPIF as the API Framework to expose APIs. This selection has several advantages:

- It is based in standards, by definition.
- It is API agnostic, meaning it can manage any API to be exposed in the Trial Network.
- It is available for 6G-SANDBOX, as Telefónica and FOGUS have developed a reference implementation in the context of EVOLVED5G ICT-41 project.
- It is becoming an ETSI Software Development Group which guarantees the relevance of this technology and provides support to standards evolution adaptation of existing source code (Roadmap).

CAPIF functional model defines several entities as displayed in Figure 5.

Figure 5: CAPIF Functional Model

CAPIF Functional model entities are described in 3GPP TS 23.222:

- The API Invoker is typically provided by a third party application provider who has service agreement with a CAPIF Provider.
- The API provider hosts one or more service APIs and has a service API arrangement with a CAPIF provider to offer the service APIs to the API Invoker.
- The CAPIF Provider and the API provider can be part of the same organization (e.g., PLMN operator), in which case the business relationship between the two is internal to a single organization. The CAPIF Provider and the API provider can be part of different organizations, in which case the business relationship between the two must exist.

API Providers have three types of entities with different roles regarding their relationship with CAPIF:

1. API Management Function: The API management function enables the API Provider to perform administration of the service APIs. The API management function consists of the following capabilities:
 - a. Auditing the service API invocation logs received from the CAPIF core function;
 - b. Monitoring the events reported by the CAPIF core function;
 - c. Configuring the API provider policies to the CAPIF core function;
 - d. Monitoring the status of the service APIs;
 - e. Onboarding the new API invokers and offboarding API invokers; and

- f. Registering and maintaining registration information of the API provider domain functions on the CAPIF core function.
2. API Publishing Function: The API publishing function enables the API provider to publish the service APIs information in order to enable the discovery of service APIs by the API invoker. The API publishing function consists of the following capability:
 - a. Publishing the service API information of the API provider to the CAPIF core function.
3. API Exposing Function: The API exposing function is the provider of the service APIs and is also the service communication entry point of the service API to the API invokers. The API exposing function consists of the following capabilities:
 - a. Authenticating the API invoker based on the identity and other information required for authentication of the API invoker provided by the CAPIF core function;
 - b. Validating the authorization provided by the CAPIF core function; and
 - c. Logging the service API invocations at the CAPIF core function.

The remaining part of this section provides a comprehensive explanation of these entities and their corresponding functionalities.

3.1 CAPIF CORE FUNCTION

CAPIF Core Function (CCF) is the key entity of the framework, as it implements all necessary functionalities to manage API exposure and consumption. The proper communication with the CCF is what characterizes an API invoker or an API provider as CAPIF-compliant. CCF serves as the central authority and data repository of the interaction between invokers and providers. The main capabilities of CCF are described below.

- **Onboarding:** The first step for an entity to be recognized as a CAPIF-compliant invoker or provider is onboarding. The candidate CAPIF user initializes communication with CCF by sending a request that includes the required security information along with the list of the APIs interested to enrol (invoker case) or to publish (provider case).
- **Authentication and Authorization:** CCF stores the security information received during the onboarding process and adopts a mutual authentication method to recognize if an entity requesting a CAPIF functionality is eligible or not. In addition, CCF is responsible for enabling authorization (via access tokens) between providers and invokers when the latter try to access the service APIs of the former.
- **API Publishing:** CCF enables all authenticated providers to expose the main attributes of their service APIs (url, http method, security method of the API, etc.) to be advertised to the invokers.
- **API Discovery:** The authenticated invokers, on the other side, using CCF discovery functionality, can receive a list of the available APIs that are authorised to access.
- **API Security Management:** CCF handles all security aspects concerning the communication among itself, invokers and providers. CCF stores a security profile for each user, thus enabling authentication and authorization.
- **API Logging and Auditing:** CCF is informed about all interactions between invokers and providers, storing crucial information on each providers API invocation (result, response, time, etc.) for further use, such as auditing purposes.
- **API Access Control Lists:** CCF requests that each service API of a provider is configured with at least one access policy to be applied to its invocation. Thus, CAPIF controls the access of service API by the invokers based on policies or usage limits.

3.2 API PROVIDERS

API Providers have three different entities that perform different tasks in relation to CCF and API Invokers. While API Management function and API Publishing Function interacts only with CCF, the API Exposing Function

interacts with API Invokers for API consumption. The consumption of APIs happens directly between API Invokers and API Exposing Functions. It is important to mention that CCF is NOT an API Gateway.

Table 1 provides the CAPIF Core Function APIs consumed by API Providers:

Table 1: CAPIF Core Function APIs consumed by API Providers

API Name	API Operation
CAPIF_API_Provider_Management_API	Register_API_Provider Update_API_Provider Deregister_API_Provider
CAPIF_Publish_Service_API	Publish_Service_API Unpublish_Service_API Update_Service_API Get_Service_API
CAPIF_Security_API	Obtain_API_Invoker_Info Revoke_Authorization
CAPIF_Logging_API_Invocation_API	Log_API_Invocation
CAPIF_Auditing_API	Query_API_Invocation_Log
CAPIF_Access_Control_Policy_API	Obtain_Access_Control_Policy
CAPIF_Routing_Info_API	Obtain_Routing_Info
CAPIF_Events_API	Subscribe_Event Notify_Event Unsubscribe_Event

3.2.1 CAPIF ONBOARDING

Onboarding CAPIF is the required operation for API Providers to be able to expose their APIs in CAPIF and consume CAPIF Core Function services. In order to Onboard CAPIF, the API Management Function within the API Provider needs to use **CAPIF_API_Provider_Management_API:: Register_API_Provider** operation.

Figure 6: API Provider Onboarding

Figure 6 shows the steps for API Provider Onboarding. The steps to complete the onboarding are the following:

1. To onboard the API provider with the CCF, the API management function initiates a registration request to the CCF. This registration request comprises a comprehensive list of details concerning all the API provider domain functions necessitating registration with the CCF, typically API Publishing function and API Exposing function.
2. Upon receipt of the registration request, the CCF conducts a thorough validation process to ensure the request's integrity. Subsequently, it generates identity and other security-related information for each of the API provider domain functions listed within the registration request.

3. The CCF then compiles the generated information into a registration response message, which it forwards to the API management function.
4. The API management function configures the received information to the individual API provider domain functions.

Each API Provider Function receives a unique ID from CCF. API Publishing Functions receive API Publishing Function IDs, while API Exposing Functions receive API Exposing Function IDs. Each API Provider Function must use its own ID when communicating with CCF.

After the API Provider Functions have been onboarded in CCF, if there are changes to be reported to CAPIF, they can use the operation **CAPIF_API_Provider_Management_API::Update_API_Provider** to update the information in the CCF. Figure 8 depicts the details of API Publishing update.

Figure 7: API Publishing update

When the API Provider wants to unregister from a CCF, it can use the operation **CAPIF_API_Provider_Management_API::Deregister_API_Provider** to remove API Provider information from CCF.

Figure 8: API Publishing deregistration

3.2.2 API PUBLISHING

Publishing APIs is the main function of the API Publishing Function within the API Provider. In order to Publish APIs, the API Publishing Function needs to use **CAPIF_Publish_Service_API::Publish_Service_API** operation. The API publishing is presented in Figure 10.

Figure 9: API Publishing

When publishing an API, the API Publishing Function must include the following information for each API:

- **apiName:** String with the API Name that will be part of the API URI: {apiRoot}/<apiName>/<apiVersion>/<apiSpecificResourceUriPart>
- **aefProfiles:** AEF profile information, which includes the exposed API details
- **description:** Text description of the API
- **supportedFeatures:** The supported optional features of the CAPIF API
- **shareableInfo:** Represents whether the service API and/or the service API category can be published to other CCFs.
- **serviceAPICategory:** The service API category to which the service API belongs to. It is relevant only for CCF to CCF interface, which is out of the scope for 6G-SANDBOX.
- **pubApiPath:** It contains the published API path within the same CAPIF provider domain. It is relevant only for CCF to CCF interface, which is out of the scope for 6G-SANDBOX.
- **ccfld:** CAPIF core function identifier which can be contacted further for discovering the details of service API information. It is relevant only for CCF to CCF interface, which is out of the scope for 6G-SANDBOX.

In the Response, the API Publishing Function will get:

- **apild:** API identifier assigned by the CAPIF core function to the published service API.

The API Publishing Function might want to remove an API from CCF. In order to remove an APIs, the API Publishing Function needs to use **CAPIF_Publish_Service_API:: Unpublish_Service_API** operation shown in Figure 11.

Figure 10: API Unpublishing

A published API shown in Figure 12 can be updated by using the **CAPIF_Publish_Service_API:: Update_Service_API** from the same API Publishing Function that did the initial publication.

Figure 11: API Update

Finally, an API Publishing Function can retrieve the list of all published APIs, or a single API. For retrieving API information published in CCF, **CAPIF_Publish_Service_API:: Get_Service_API** method should be used.

Figure 12: API GetService

3.2.3 API REQUESTS AUTHENTICATION

The entity exposing APIs to API Invokers within API Providers is the API Exposing function. API Exposing Functions will get API invocations from API Invokers according to the Security Methods specified by the API Provider when publishing the APIs in CAPIF. The API Provider can specify three different Security Methods to be supported, as described in TS 33.122 [1]. The three security methods supported by the standard are:

1. Method 1 – Using TLS-PSK: Based in a generated pre-shared key
2. Method 2 – Using PKI: Using Certificates
3. Method 3 – TLS with OAuth 2.0 token

In 6G-SANDBOX, we will be using only Method 3, OAuth 2.0 token. Therefore, API Invokers willing to consume APIs from 6G Library will need to get the OAuth 2.0 token. With the token obtained, the API Invoker will consume the API sending the token in the header Authorization: Bearer <jwt-token>.

When receiving the API request, API Exposing Function must get the token from the HTTP header and check the validity of the token and the scope defined.

The format for tokens is described in TS 33.122 and specifies both the AEF_ID and the apiName that the API Invoker wants to consume:

- 3gpp#aefld1:apiName1,apiName2,...apiNameX;aefld2:apiName1,apiName2,...apiNameY;...aefldN:apiName1,apiName2,...apiNameZ

API Exposing Function must check that the AEF_ID in the token corresponds to its own AEF_ID assigned by CAPIF during the onboarding process, and that the apiName corresponds to the API being consumed.

3.2.4 ACCESS CONTROL LISTS - ACLS

Access Control Lists are created by CCF to define API policies. It is not specified by 3GPP how these lists must be defined or created; it is subject to the implementation of the CAPIF standard.

CCF in 6G-SANDBOX creates an ACL every time an API Invoker request a Security Context. If there is no ACL associated to the (API Invoker, API ID) duple, a new ACL is created. The ACL specifies the number of API invocations the API Invoker can consume until a new Security Context is demanded.

The responsibility to enforce the Service Level Agreement (SLA) linked to the Access Control List (ACL) lies with the AEFs, as the API invocation occurs directly between API Invokers and AEFs. Therefore, AEFs need to retrieve the ACL policy upon the first API invocation or upon receiving an event on a new ACL update (`ACCESS_CONTROL_POLICY_UPDATE`).

AEFs can obtain ACL policies using **CAPIF_Access_Control_Policy API::Obtain_Access_Control_Policy** operation.

Figure 13: ACL request

Once the AEF has the ACL policy for the API Invoker, it can control API invocations coming from the API Invoker. When the API Invoker consumes all authorised API invocations, the AEF must revoke the authorization to the API Invoker to access the API. AEFs can revoke the Authorization to an API Invoker using **CAPIF_Security API::Revoke_Authorization** operation shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Revoke API Authorization from AEF

Figure 15 shows the steps of Revoke API Authorization from AEF. When CCF removes the Authorization to an Onboarded Invoker, if the Invoker is subscribed to Events, the API Invoker will get an “API_INVOKER_AUTHORIZATION_REVOKED” event from CCF.

3.2.5 API LOGGING AND AUDITING

API Logging is the capability offered by CCF to register API consumption from the API Providers. API consumptions by API Invokers can be registered in CCF for charging or auditing purposes. In order to Log API consumptions in CCF, the API Exposing Function within the API Provider shown in Figure 16 needs to use **CAPIF_Logging_API_Invocation API:: Log_API_Invocation** operation.

Figure 15: API Logging

API Logs can be queried by API Providers. API Logs can be consulted by the API Management Function within the API Providers. API Management Function needs to use **CAPIF_Auditing API:: Query_API_Invocation_Log** operation.

Figure 16: API Auditing

3.2.6 CCF EVENTS

The CAPIF core function enables the subscribing entity (API invoker, API exposing function, API publishing function, API management function) to subscribe to and unsubscribe from the CAPIF events such as availability events of service APIs, change in service API information, monitoring service API invocations, API invoker onboarding events, etc.

Table 2: CAPIF Events

Events	Events Description	Events Names
Availability of service APIs	Availability events of service APIs (e.g. active, inactive)	SERVICE_API_AVAILABLE SERVICE_API_UNAVAILABLE
Service API updated	Events related to change in service API information	SERVICE_API_UPDATE
Monitoring service API invocations	Events corresponding to service API invocations	SERVICE_API_INVOCATION_SUCCESS SERVICE_API_INVOCATION_FAILURE
API invoker status	Events related to API invoker status in CAPIF (onboarded, offboarded)	API_INVOKER_ONBOARDED API_INVOKER_OFFBOARDED API_INVOKER_AUTHORIZATION_REVOKED API_INVOKER_UPDATED
API topology hiding status	Events related to API topology hiding status in CAPIF (created, revoked)	API_TOPOLOGY_HIDING_CREATED API_TOPOLOGY_HIDING_REVOKED
Access Control Lists Event	Events related to ACLs	ACCESS_CONTROL_POLICY_UPDATE ACCESS_CONTROL_POLICY_UNAVAILABLE

Subscribing entities that want to receive Events from CCF, need to use **CAPIF_Events API:: Subscribe_Event** operation. When subscribing to Events, the subscribing entity must include the following information:

- **events**: list of CAPIF Events the subscribing entity wants to subscribe to.
- **eventFilters**: the subscribing entity can filter by Apild, InvokerID or Aefld.
- **eventReq**: reporting information.
- **notificationDestination**: the callback URI where CCF will send the Events to.
- **requestTestNotification**: Set to true by Subscriber to request the CAPIF core function to send a test notification.
- **websockNotifConfig**: the configuration information for the delivery of notifications over Websockets.
- **supportedFeatures**: the features supported by an API

After the successful subscription, the subscribing entity will get information on the subscribed events plus the SubscriptionId embedded in the HTTPS header Location:

- **Location**: Contains the URI of the newly created resource, according to the structure:

```
{apiRoot}/capif-events/v1/{subscriberId}/subscriptions/{subscriptionId}
```


Figure 17: CAPIF Event Subscription

When an Event is generated by CCF, it must get the list of Subscriptions to this event and send the Event Notifications as displayed in Figure 18:

Figure 18: CAPIF Events flow

Subscribing entities that want to stop receiving Events from CCF, needs to use **CAPIF_Events API:: Unsubscribe_Event** operation. When unsubscribing to Events, the subscribing entity must use the resource created in the subscription operation:

```
{apiRoot}/capif-events/v1/{subscriberId}/subscriptions/{subscriptionId}
```


Figure 19: CAPIF Event Unsubscription

3.2.7 AEF GATEWAY

CAPIF allows services to be exposed, but many of them cannot be directly integrated because they must perform onboarding as provider, publish the service, check the authorization when an Invoker wants to use it, etc. Integrating these operations into an API already implemented, can be become complex or even not possible. With this problem in mind, we have developed a solution that is responsible for carrying out basic operations with CAPIF and thus facilitate the integration of other APIs, the AEF Gateway.

The AEF Gateway is a service that acts as a gateway between existing APIs and CAPIF and is responsible for facilitating their integration. With this, the existing APIs delegate the onboarding as Provider or publishing into CAPIF to the AEF Gateway. The APIs simply must be added to the AEF GW so that the redirection is carried out when an Invoker wants to access them.

Figure 20: AEF Gateway model

Existing APIs are published in CAPIF by the APF with the aim that Invokers can discover and use them to access the APIs that it exposes. When an API Invoker makes a request to the service to use an API, the AEF GW is responsible for verifying that the request is correct, and the invoker has permission to use the API it wants. If it has permission, it will redirect the request to the existing API, which simply must return the response to the request coming from the AEF Gateway. If it does not have permission, the AEF GW will return the corresponding error indicating to the Invoker that it does not have permission to use the API.

3.3 API INVOKERS

API Invokers are the entities defined by 3GPP functional model as the ones consuming APIs exposed by API Exposing Functions. The consumption of APIs happens directly between API Invokers and API Exposing Functions. It is important to mention that CAPIF Core Function is NOT an API Gateway.

Figure 21: API Invocation model

API Invokers consumes the following APIs from CAPIF Core Function:

Table 3: CAPIF Core Function APIs consumed by API Invokers

API Name	API Operations
CAPIF_API_Invoker_management API	Onboard_API_Invoker Offboard_API_Invoker
CAPIF_Discover_Service_API	Discover_Service_API
CAPIF_Security API	Obtain_Security_Method Obtain_Authorization
CAPIF_Events API	Subscribe_Event Notify_Event Unsubscribe_Event

These API operations are described in the following subsections:

3.3.1 CAPIF ONBOARDING/OFFBOARDING

Onboarding CAPIF is the required operation for API Invokers to be able to consume CAPIF Core Function services. In order to onboard CAPIF, API Invokers need to use **CAPIF_API_Invoker_management API::Onboard_API_Invoker** operation.

Figure 22: CAPIF Onboarding

The steps to complete the onboarding are:

1. As a preliminary step in the onboarding process, the API invoker acquires onboarding enrolment data from the API provider's domain. This onboarding enrolment information plays a vital role in authenticating and establishing a secure TLS communication channel with the CAPIF core function during the onboarding procedure. This enrolment information encompasses essential details of the CAPIF core function, such as its address and Root CA certificate, along with an integral onboarding credential, represented by the OAuth 2.0 access token [2]. The procedure used to obtain the enrolment information by the API invoker is not specified by 3GPP.
2. The API invoker and the CAPIF core function will establish a secure session utilizing TLS with server-side certificate authentication. The API invoker will utilize the enrolment information obtained in the previous step to initiate the TLS session with the CAPIF core function. This operation is the only one that is carried out over a server-side-only TLS connection.
3. Upon the successful establishment of the TLS session, the API invoker will transmit an Onboard API Invoker request message to the CAPIF core function, including the enrolment credential in the form of an OAuth 2.0 [4] access token. As part of this process, the API invoker will generate a key pair consisting of a Private Key and a Public Key, providing the Public Key alongside the Onboard API Invoker request.
4. The CAPIF core function will validate the enrolment credential, specifically the OAuth 2.0 access token. Upon successful validation, the CAPIF core function will proceed to generate an API invoker's profile as outlined in TS 23.222 [3]. This profile may encompass details such as the chosen method for authentication and authorization between the API Invoker and the AEF. Additionally, the CAPIF core function has the option to autonomously generate an API invoker's certificate, uniquely tied to the assigned API invoker identity and public key. This certificate serves a pivotal role in subsequent authentication procedures between the API invoker and the CAPIF core function, as well as in establishing secure connections and authenticating with the API Exposing Function.
5. The CAPIF core function will provide a response in the form of an Onboard API Invoker response message. This response will encompass several crucial elements, including:
 - a. API Invoker ID: unique ID that identifies the API Invoker towards CAPIF Core Function
 - b. API Invoker's Certificate: This certificate is needed for mutual TLS authentication between the API Invoker and CAPIF Core Function for all API requests.

Offboarding process is simpler from an API Invokers perspective (see Figure 23)

Figure 23: CAPIF Offboarding

With the API Invokers Certificate and the API Invoker ID, the API Invoker uses the **CAPIF_API_Invoker_management_API::Offboard_API_Invoker** operation to request the Offboarding to CAPIF Core Function. CAPIF Core Function will response to the request and tear down the TLS connection.

After the API Invoker is offboarded, the API Invoker ID will be invalidated and cannot be reused.

3.3.2 API DISCOVERY

API Invokers can Discover APIs that are published in CAPIF. CCF contains all the APIs that have been published by AEFs. In order to get the list of APIs a CCF is managing, API Invoker needs to use **CAPIF_Discover_Service_API::Discover_Service_API** operation.

Figure 24: API Discovery

When requesting the list of APIs, API Invokers can set up some filters such as api-name, api-version, aef-id, preferred-aef-location among others. Upon successful response (200 OK), CCF returns in the response body a collection of ServiceAPIDescriptions that matches with the filters specified in the request.

3.3.3 OBTAINING SECURITY CONTEXT

API Invokers need to request a Security Context in order to be able to consume APIs. API Invokers will use **CAPIF_Discover_Service_API::Obtain_Security_Method** operation.

Figure 25: Security Context Request

The API invoker initiates an Obtain Service API Authorization request to the CAPIF core function, seeking permission to access the service API. This request includes essential API invoker identity information and any data required for authenticating the API invoker.

The CAPIF core function validates the authentication of the API invoker, utilizing the provided authentication information. Furthermore, it assesses whether the API invoker possesses the necessary authorization to access the requested service API. The authentication process is detailed in 3GPP TS 33.122.

The authorization information required to access the service APIs is transmitted back to the API invoker as part of the Obtain Service API Authorization Response. As already mentioned, in 6G-SANDBOX we will be using Method 3 from the available ones (i.e., TLS with OAuth 2.0 token) to support security between API Invokers and AEFs.

Figure 26: Method 3 based in OAuth 2.0 tokens

In this method, CCF is the one expediting the OAuth 2.0 Tokens to API Invokers.

3.3.4 API CONSUMPTION

API Consumption between API Invokers and AEFs happens directly. API Invokers need to send authentication information to AEFs for them to validate the request and decide to let it progress or refuse it. As explained in section 3.3.3, in 6G-SANDBOX we will be using OAuth 2.0 Tokens for API Invokers authentication in AEFs.

Figure 27: API Invocation between API Invoker and AEF

API Invokers need to generate an Access Token Request to get the OAuth 2.0 token. The Access Token Request contains the following information elements:

- **grant_type**: the value for this field must be "client_credentials"
- **client_id**: matches API Invoker ID
- **client_secret**: if present, it must match the shared secret specified in the onboarding process.
- **scope**: when present shall contain a list of AEF identifiers and its associated API names for which the access_token is authorized for use.

The format for defining the Scope for the Token is the following:

- 3gpp#aefld1:apiName1,apiName2,...apiNameX;aefld2:apiName1,apiName2,...apiNameY;...aefldN:apiName1,apiName2,...apiNameZ

The format uses delimiter "#" after the discriminator "3gpp", ":" after AEF identifier, "," between API names and ";" between the last API name of the previous AEF identifier and the next AEF identifier.

CCF will process the Token Request and return an Access Token Response in the body of the response. The Access Token Response contains the following information:

- **access_token**: WS Compact Serialized representation of JWS signed JSON object (AccessTokenClaims)
- **token_type**: value will be "Bearer"
- **expires_in**: duration of the token expressed in seconds
- **scope**: the list of AEFs and APIs for which the token provides authorization

4 CAPIF DEPLOYMENT AND EXPANSION ACTIVITIES

4.1 DEPLOYMENT OF CCF IN KUBERNETES

CCF is a 6GLibrary object that can be deployed inside a Trial Network, to expose the APIs of the Trial Network components. CCF is an API Manager that will be available at 6G-SANDBOX Facility Level, as well, to expose the APIs of each facility.

CCF will be based on CAPIF Core function implementation by Telefónica and Fogus that will be published at ETSI Open CAPIF Software Group (https://ocf.etsi.org/news/20231105_opencapif_launch/).

Figure 28: OpenCAPIF Logo by ETSI

In order to deploy CCF in Kubernetes cluster, 6G-SANDBOX is providing a Helm Chart as part of the 6GLibrary repository for 6G-SANDBOX facilities to deploy it.

The Helm Chart has the following dependencies:

4.1.1.1 INGRESS CONTROLLER

If not exists Ingress in cluster, use the next command to install it.

```
$ helm upgrade --install ingress-nginx ingress-nginx --repo https://kubernetes.github.io/ingress-nginx --set rbac.create=true --set controller.service.type=NodePort
```

OPTIONAL - if you need specify the nodePort in cluster use

```
$ helm upgrade --install ingress-nginx ingress-nginx --repo https://kubernetes.github.io/ingress-nginx --set rbac.create=true --set controller.service.type=NodePort --set controller.service.nodePorts.http=32080 --set controller.service.nodePorts.https=32443 --namespace ingress-nginx --create-namespace --set controller.extraArgs."enable-ssl-passthrough=true" --kubeconfig ../oneke-new.kubeconfig
```

Check if ssl-passthrough is enabled in nginx controller.

```
$ kubectl -n ingress-nginx get deploy -o yaml | grep passthrough
```

4.1.1.2 PROMETHEUS

You can install prometheus however, you will need permissions to deploy prometheus in the cluster. The Helm Chart creates a ClusterRole to access to all resources in the cluster.

In case you don't have permission or already there is provided a Prometheus in the cluster. in capif/values.yaml gives the field **monitoring.prometheus.enable**: ""

Grafana will require the endpoint to prometheus. Please keep in mind setup the grafana's field in capif/values.yaml

4.1.1.3 VAULT

An instance of vault is required. If the cluster doesn't provide the vault instance, you can install it following the next steps:

```
$ helm repo add hashicorp https://helm.releases.hashicorp.com
```

```
$ helm upgrade --install vault hashicorp/vault -n mon --set server.dev.enabled=true --set server.dev.devRootToken="dev-only-token" --create-namespace
```

if you are using ingress controller, please use:

```
$ helm upgrade --install vault hashicorp/vault -n mon --set server.dev.enabled=true --set server.dev.devRootToken="dev-only-token" --set server.ingress.enabled=true --set server.ingress.hosts[0].host="vault.mon.int" --set server.ingress.ingressClassName=nginx --create-namespace
```

verify pods are running

```
$ kubectl -n mon get pods
```

Once the vault is provided in the cluster. You need to create the PKI and certificates. Follow the vault-job step to create it.

4.1.1.3.1 CREATING VAULT PKI AND CERTIFICATES

If you change values by default in the capi/values.yaml. Please, consider have a look of some topics.

- You will need to create PKI and certificates, therefore. The VAULT_TOKEN provided must have sufficient permissions in Vault to create it.
- Modify:
 - **namespace** in vault-job/vault-job.yaml. The namespace should be changed in the entire file. By default, is mon (same namespace when CAPIF is deployed)
 - export **VAULT_ADDR** using the service deployed to vault. By default, is <http://vault-internal:8200>
 - export **VAULT_TOKEN** using the token created to vault. By default, is dev-only-token.
 - **DOMAIN1** - variable used for generate certificate (CSR) to capi (ex: DOMAIN1=capif.mobile.cloud)

```
$ kubectl apply -f vault-job/
```

- Setup the **parametersVault.env.VaultHostname**: This is the endPoint to vault. This endpoint can be a service/ingress of Kubernetes.
- Setup **parametersVault.env.VaultPort**: This is the port listening to vault instance.
- Setup **parametersVault.env.vaultAccessToken**: This is the token used for CAPIF to create the certificates in vault. If vault owns of you. Use the token created in [vault](#). Otherwise, the admin of the cluster will provide you the token. This token will need sufficient permissions to create PKI and certificates.

4.1.1.4 CAPIF CONFIGURATION

Please, have a look of [values.yaml](#) file and setup according of the conditions

4.1.1.5 CCF DEPLOYMENT USING HELM CHART

download dependencies

```
$ helm dependency build capi/
```

use the AWS credentials to login AWS ECR, once that, create a secrets

```
$ kubectl create secret docker-registry regcred --docker-password=$(aws ecr get-login-password) --  
namespace=mon --docker-server=709233559969.dkr.ecr.eu-central-1.amazonaws.com --docker-  
username="AWS"
```

```
# check ingress_ip.oneke
```

```
kubectl get svc -A | grep nginx
```

```
# install capif
```

```
$ helm upgrade --install -n mon monitoring-capif capif/ --set nginx.nginx.env.capifHostname=mon-  
capif.monitoring.int --set ingress_ip.oneke="10.17.173.127" --set env=oneke --atomic --create-namespace
```

NOTE: The deployment can take as long as 8 minutes to be ready.

4.1.2 CAPIF SERVICES EXPOSED

CAPIF Core Function implementation is based in Containers. There is one Container per Service (API) offered by CCF. The list of containers exposing services is the following:

- Invoker Management API: Service to register new Invokers in CAPIF
- Provider Management API: Service to register new Providers in CAPIF
- Discover API: Service used by Invoker to discover Services registered in CAPIF
- Publish API: Service used by APF to publish new Services in CAPIF
- Events API: Service used by all Entities of CAPIF to receive notifications (New service Published, Provider removed, etc)
- Security API: Service used by Invokers to create security context and manage security auth between Invokers and Services
- Logging/Auditing API: Services to save and consult logs of use when Invoker calls Service.
- Access Control Policy API: Service used by an API exposing function to obtain the access control policy from the CAPIF core function.
- Routing Info API: Service used by an API exposing function to obtain the API routing information from the CAPIF core function.

Services are exposed using NGINX as a reverse proxy supporting mutual TLS negotiation. All CAPIF API requests are coming to NGINX that handles the certificates negotiation for TLS mutual authentication and dispatches the request to the specific service consumed.

Figure 29: CAPIF Core Function Services

All data is persisted in a MongoDB [4] database. This database contains the information about registered Invokers, AEFs, Security Contexts issued, Logs, etc.

Vault [5] is the Certificate Authority included in CAPIF Core Function. This CA is responsible for expediting all certificates requested by API Invokers and AEFs.

REDIS [6] is used by CCF as a bus for internal communication between services and manages the CAPIF Events triggering.

Finally, the Register Service is a Service that is out of the scope of CAPIF Standards, and is responsible to provide the following information to API Invokers and AEFs:

- CAPIF Core Function address: the DNS or IP address of CAPIF Core Function to request Onboarding.
- CA Root certificate: Root certificate needed to validate Server-side Certificates.
- OAuth 2.0 Token: Token for the Onboarding operation in CCF. This is the only operation which is server-side only TLS and the Token provides the additional security from the Client side.

Figure 30: CAPIF Register Service information

The address for the Register service will be in the format “ccf.malaga.6gsandbox.eu” (This URL is provided as an example).

CAPIF Core Function will publish CAPIF APIs following the 3GPP URL specifications. The way 3GPP forms URLs for APIs follows this format:

{apiRoot}/api-name/v1

In 6G-SANDBOX case, for Málaga platform, the apiRoot will be “https://ccf.malaga.6gsandbox.eu”. The API names are the ones specified by 3GPP in TS 23.222 and 29.222 [7].

Table 4: CAPIF Core Function API URLs

CAPIF Service	API Name	URL
Discover Service	/service-apis/v1	https://ccf.malaga.6gsandbox.eu/service-apis/v1
Publish Service	/published-apis/v1	https://ccf.malaga.6gsandbox.eu/published-apis/v1
Events Service	/capif-events/v1	https://ccf.malaga.6gsandbox.eu/capif-events/v1
Invoker Management API	/api-invoker-management/v1	https://ccf.malaga.6gsandbox.eu/api-invoker-management/v1
Security API	/capif-security/v1	https://ccf.malaga.6gsandbox.eu/capif-security/v1
Logging API	/api-invocation-logs/v1	https://ccf.malaga.6gsandbox.eu/api-invocation-logs/v1
Auditing API	/logs/v1	https://ccf.malaga.6gsandbox.eu/logs/v1
Access Control Policy API	/access-control-policy/v1	https://ccf.malaga.6gsandbox.eu/access-control-policy/v1
Provider Management API	/api-provider-management/v1	https://ccf.malaga.6gsandbox.eu/api-provider-management/v1
Routing Info API	/capif-routing-info/v1	https://ccf.malaga.6gsandbox.eu/capif-routing-info/v1

These endpoints should be used when consuming any of CAPIF Core Function APIs. For example, to Discover APIs, GET /allServiceAPIs method is defined. Therefore, the URL that the API Invoker should build to consume the API will be:

GET https://ccf.malaga.6gsandbox.eu/service-apis/v1/allServiceAPIs

4.2 EXPAND CAPIF WITH A MANAGEMENT TOOL

The CAPIF Management tool is a user interface designed to streamline the interaction and control of the underlying CAPIF functionalities. This frontend serves as a graphical interface, enhancing user experience and providing a seamless way to manage CAPIF resources.

4.2.1 WEB INTERFACE

The web interface is a user interface that allows interaction with CAPIF systems through a web browser. It is developed using React, a popular JavaScript library for building user interfaces. The web interface presents a login window, serving as the entry point for users to access the management tool. The use of React allows a dynamic and responsive design, providing an efficient and seamless user experience during the login process and through the entire web application.

Figure 31: CAPIF Management Tool login interface.

The login page serves as the gateway to a comprehensive management experience, allowing authorized users to access and oversee various functionalities. With the appropriate permissions, users can log in to the system, gaining the necessary authority to perform tasks related to API configuration, user management, and monitoring of invokers and providers. In essence, the login process serves as the key to unlock a range of powerful management capabilities, tailored to the specific permissions of each user.

4.2.2 INVOKERS MANAGEMENT

The Invokers page offers a concise display of available invokers, featuring their names and unique IDs. This simplified interface allows users to list and individually access invokers for management purposes.

Figure 32: CAPIF Management Tool invoker's page.

The Invoker page offers a comprehensive view of an individual invoker, detailing its connected APIs. Administrators can manage API access, deleting some APIs access. The page also features a timeline of recent events, providing real-time insights into the invoker's activities. This centralized space ensures efficient and informed management, allowing for dynamic adjustments to the invoker's capabilities based on evolving system requirements.

Figure 33: CAPIF Management Tool invoker view.

4.2.3 AEF MANAGEMENT

The Providers page offers a concise display of available invokers, featuring their names and unique IDs. This simplified interface allows users to list and individually access providers for management purposes.

Figure 34: CAPIF Management Tool provider's page.

When you enter a provider's page, you get access to the provider, the list of exposed APIs along with the option to remove any of them. Additionally, the page presents a timeline of the provider's recent events, offering real-time information about its activities.

Figure 35: CAPIF Management Tool provider view.

4.2.4 SECURITY CONTEXT MANAGEMENT

The Users page presents a comprehensive list of users in the system, offering the capability to easily delete any profile. Opting for deletion not only removes the user's profile but also eliminates associated roles such as invoker or provider if they possess either.

Figure 36: CAPIF Management Tool user's page.

To remove an invoker's security context for a specific API, simply navigate to that invoker's profile and remove access to one of the APIs. Similarly, if a provider wants to remove an exposed service, go to the provider's page, and remove the specific service.

4.2.5 CAPIF MONITORING

The landing page offers a quick and straightforward overview of the entities currently present in CAPIF. It provides a snapshot of the system, allowing users to swiftly grasp the existing invokers, providers, and users, facilitating efficient navigation and management of the CAPIF ecosystem.

Figure 37: CAPIF Management Tool home dashboard.

The Grafana page provides dynamic visualizations through graphs, showcasing essential insights into system performance. From the number of running Docker containers to memory usage and CPU metrics, these graphs offer an intuitive, real-time snapshot of the system's health and performance. Grafana's interface streamlines monitoring, allowing users to easily grasp the behaviour of key resources in a view.

Figure 38: CAPIF Management Tool Grafana dashboard.

5 CAPIF INTEGRATION INTO 6G LIBRARY

CAPIF Core Function is integrated as a component inside 6GLibrary. It is a component that is mandatory in the 6G-SANDBOX facilities. Each 6G-SANDBOX compute and connect infrastructure must have at least one CAPIF Core Function deployed to expose APIs.

Figure 39: Trial Network concept depicting also the CCF deployed in Kubernetes

CCF is a 6G Library object that Experimenters will be able to add to their Trial Networks. By doing so, the Experimenters will have a CCF deployed inside the Trial Network connected to the “Service VLAN” to expose CCF interface outside the Trial Network.

Other components inside the Trial Network (e.g., a NEF) can expose their APIs using CAPIF, and they also can consume APIs as API Invokers.

The following subsections explain the repositories used for CAPIF and how the instantiation of CAPIF inside the Trial Network takes place. It also explains how to interact with CAPIF once it is deployed.

5.1 6G-SANDBOX LIBRARY REPOSITORY

6G-Library repository is available for all experimenters intending to deploy a Trial Network in 6G-SANDBOX, using specific components and configurations. The library contains all the modules and physical equipment that experimenter can select to configure the Trial Network.

6G-Library Public

Watch 2 Fork 0 Star 1

main 3 branches 0 tags

Go to file Add file Code

File/Folder	Description	Time
.global	Adding first components (#2)	3 days ago
.sites	Adding first components (#2)	3 days ago
dummy-component	Adding first components (#2)	3 days ago
skel	Adding first components (#2)	3 days ago
tn_bastion	BUG: Fix problem with terraform a VM nics in OpenNebula	2 days ago
tn_bootstrap	Adding first components (#2)	3 days ago
tn_vxlan	Adding first components (#2)	3 days ago
vm_kvm_very_small	BUG: Fix problem with terraform a VM nics in OpenNebula	2 days ago
vxlan	Adding first components (#2)	3 days ago
README.md	Adding first components (#2)	3 days ago

6G-SANDBOX SNS Library

6G-SANDBOX is a HE funded research project (HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022-STREAM-C-01-01). The 6G-SANDBOX project brings a complete and modular facility for the European experimentation ecosystem (in line and under the directions set by SNS JU), which is expected to support for the next decade technology and research validation processes needed in the pathway towards 6G.

Languages

- Jinja 50.0%
- Groovy 49.1%
- HCL 0.9%

Figure 40: 6G Library GitHub repository

A Trial Network should be a fully configurable, manageable and controllable environment, combining virtual and physical components and modelling a 6G network environment, allowing experiments to be executed, capturing a multitude of KPIs so that new technologies could be validated.

The structure of the repository is shown in Figure 41 and was explained in detail in Section 2.2.

In summary, each component is represented in a folder, which includes public, private and doc folders. As an example, there are some components already available, such as `tn_bastion` (which is a VM that acts as bastion for a Trial Network), `tn_bootstrap` (which is the meta component that create the context to run a Trial Network) and `tn_vxlan` (that creates VXLAN network for Trial Network Bootstrap).

The repository is accessible in <https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library>.

5.2 CAPIF REPOSITORY

CAPIF repository in 6G-SANDBOX has been forked from EVOLVED5G public repository. This is a temporal solution till ETSI OpenCAPIF [8] repository becomes populated with initial code seed. This code seed is expected to happen in January 2024.

The repository used in 6G-SANDBOX is https://github.com/Telefonica/CAPIF_Future_Network_Lab, which is a Private repository for Telefónica organization.

CAPIF_Future_Network_Lab Private

Unwatch 6 Fork 0 Star 0

main 8 branches 4 tags

Go to file Add file Code

andresanaya21 Merge pull request #136 from Telefonica/ingress-register 2d8fe66 2 days ago 604 commits

File	Description	Updated
.github/workflows	ports	last week
cicd	linting_code	last month
docs	upload capif develop	5 months ago
helm	nginx register using letsencrypt certificate	2 days ago
monitoring	overwrite grafana config with enable iframes	last week
pac	upload capif develop	5 months ago
prometheus	prometheus	5 months ago
services	fix events	last week
tests	Remove wrong tests cases placed under tests/resources	last week
tools	Fix ubuntu version for robot image and minor fix on 'if' present at ...	3 months ago
.gitignore	modified name of helm	last month
CITATION.cff	upload capif develop	5 months ago
LICENSE	helmifying capif	2 weeks ago
README.md	update reamde	last month

README.md

Common API Framework (CAPIF)

- [Common API Framework \(CAPIF\)](#)
- [Repository structure](#)
- [CAPIF_API_Services](#)
 - [How to run CAPIF services in this Repository](#)
 - [Run All CAPIF Services locally with Docker images](#)
 - [Run All CAPIF Services locally with Docker images and deploy monitoring stack](#)
 - [Run each service using Docker](#)
 - [Run each service using Python](#)
- [How to test CAPIF APIs](#)
 - [Test Plan Documentation](#)
 - [Robot Framework](#)
 - [Using Curl](#)
 - [Using PostMan \(only for release 1.0 of CAPIF\)](#)
- [Important uris:](#)
 - [Mongo DB Dashboard](#)
- [CAPIF Tool Release 1.0](#)
- [CAPIF Tool Release 2.0](#)
- [CAPIF Tool Release 2.1](#)
- [CAPIF Tool Release 3.0](#)
- [CAPIF Tool Release 3.1](#)
- [CAPIF Tool Release 3.1.1](#)
- [CAPIF Tool Release 3.1.2](#)
- [CAPIF Tool Release 3.1.3](#)

Figure 41: CAPIF Repository in Telefónica Github organization

5.3 CAPIF DESCRIPTION AS 6G LIBRARY OBJECT

CAPIF will be available as a component in the 6G library, as all other components to be deployed in the trial Networks. An experimenter will be able to include an instance of CAPIF within their Trial Network, providing the experiment with a component where other components can publish their APIs (as Providers) that are discoverable and consumable by other components (as Invokers), following the standard defined by 3GPP.

CAPIF has been developed following the recommended principles of the Cloud Native Foundation (Scalable, Resilient, Manageable, Observable, Automated). It is composed of a set of microservices designed to be deployed in a standard Kubernetes cluster in a simple and standard way.

CAPIF is composed of multiple microservices and requires the existence of other functionalities on which it relies on. For the deployment of CAPIF in a Trial Network, it is necessary to have a series of functionalities, which will be deployed beforehand using other components of the 6G library, and these are indicated in CAPIF's own public information manifesto.

```

capif > public > ! description.yaml
1 #####
2 ##
3 ## Component metadata
4 ##
5 #####
6 component_name: "capif"
7 family: general
8 maintainers:
9   - Jesus Macias Portela <jesus.maciasportela@telefonica.com>
10 version: 0.0.1
11 depends:
12   - oneKE (>= 0.0.1)
13   - vault (>= 0.0.1)
14 short_description: This component deploy CAPIF component inside a Trial Network
15 long_description: |
16   This component deploy CAPIF component as part of a Trial Network. The deployment consist on multiple microservices
17   deployed on a kubernetes cluster that exposes various services:
18   - CCF endpoint
19   - Register Service endpoint
20   CAPIF has been implemented following 3GPP Release 17 specifications
21 platforms: [one]
22 sites: [uma]
23

```

Figure 42: CAPIF 6G Object Description

Current component version is ready to be deployed on a 6G-SANDBOX site with OpenNebula (one) as a private cloud, to take advantage of the deployment service for Kubernetes provided by OpenNebula: oneKE.

In the component manifest, the components on which its deployment depends are specified. This is relevant for the TNLCM, because it needs to know all dependencies to be able to create the dependency tree to define the order in which components must be deployed.

CAPIF dependency tree:

1. ONEKE
 - 1.1. VXLAN
2. VAULT
 - 2.1. ONEKE
3. CAPIF
 - 3.1. ONEKE
 - 3.2. VAULT

CAPIF has two dependencies, VAULT and ONEKE, which in turn have their own dependencies. The TNLCM is in charge of computing all the dependencies and launching the deployment of each component in the appropriate order, collecting the output information necessary to be used as input for the deployment of the next component.

The definition of a component in the 6G library is based on specifying a series of input parameters, both public and private, and a series of output parameters. This assumption allows to abstract the deployment of the component as if it were a black box where we know the input and output interface.

Figure 43: 6G Object Abstraction

5.3.1 CAPIF INPUTS

To deploy a component, the TNLCM is responsible for generating the necessary inputs that will come from different sources:

1. The list of public variables that can be modified by the experimenter.
2. The list of private variables that are necessary to carry out the deployment but cannot be modified by the experimenter.
3. The list of variables added by the TNLCM to orchestrate the deployment.

This process helps manage the deployment inputs, distinguishing between variables that can be customized by the experimenter (public), those essential for deployment (but not to be altered, private), and the additional variables introduced by the deployment orchestrator for smooth execution.

```

! 04_input_capif.yaml
1  #FROM TNLCM
2  tn_lcm_callback: "http://tnlcm.inet/TN/callback"
3  tn_id: "xczsf1"
4
5  # FROM PUBLIC VARIABLES SECTION
6  monitoring: true
7  k8s_external_ip: "10.11.28.99"
8  capif_hostname: "ccf.xczsf1.6gsandbox.priv"
9  vault_hostname: "vault.xczsf1.6gsandbox.priv"
10 vault_port: 3788
11 vault_token: "dmF1bHQgdG9rZW4="
12
13 # FROM PRIVATE VARIABLES SECTION (ONLY FOR ADVANCED USERS)
14 install_nginx_ingress: true
15 install_skooner_dashboard: true
  
```

Figure 44: CAPIF 6G Object inputs

5.3.2 CAPIF OUTPUTS

Once a component has been successfully deployed, there is a list of output results with the relevant information for the component. In the case of the CAPIF, no output parameters are indicated. If the deployment has completed successfully, the service will be available at the URLs specified in the inputs.

Figure 45: CAPIF Deployed in Kubernetes inside a Trial Network

5.4 CAPIF INSTANTIATION AS PART OF A TRIAL NETWORK

Any experiment includes the CCF as a 6G Library object, and thus the TNLCM will be responsible for deploying it. TNLCM will use Jenkins Pipeline to deploy the different 6G Library objects according to dependencies. CCF object has dependencies with ONEKE (Kubernetes cluster). CCF images are built to be ready to boot CCF. Upon deployment completion, the Ansible part of CCF Component will issue the commands required to start CCF, as described in section 6.2.1:

```
./run.sh
```

The URL that CCF will use in the trial network will be: `ccf.<trial network domain>`, being `<trial network domain>` the DNS domain defined for this specific trial network.

Once the Trial Network has been instantiated, the Experimenter can use the sanity check described in section 6.2.2 to verify that CCF is working properly.

5.5 USING OPEN APIs FROM TRIAL NETWORKS

Upon Trial Network deployment, CCF will be up and running enabling the publication of APIs from API Providers and the onboarding of API Invokers. Some 6G Library objects will publish their APIs in CAPIF by default. For example, if the Trial Network contains a 5G Core with NEF, NEF will act as API Provider in this case and publish all NEF APIs implemented in CAPIF.

Along with CCF, CAPIF will include a Registration Service to enable API Invokers and API Providers to onboard CAPIF. This registration service is Out-Of-Scope of CAPIF 3GPP Technical Specifications. 6G-SANDBOX will provide this Registration Service to facilitate the usage of CAPIF.

6 CAPIF LIFECYCLE

CCF is a software component, and as any other software, it uses Versions from Releases that includes new functionality and bug fixing. At this point in 6G-SANDBOX project we will use the initial release from OpenCAPIF, but it is expected that new releases will come out in the next years. In this section, we anticipate how to manage this release upgrades when they will be published. This management is structured in a Day 0/Day 1 /Day 2+ which is an industry standard to approach lifecycle descriptions.

6.1 CAPIF DAY 0 OPERATION

6.1.1 ENVIRONMENT PREPARATION

CAPIF has been developed using Containers technology. It can run in Docker environment but for 6G-SANDBOX we have selected Kubernetes as the environment to execute CAPIF. The dependencies to deploy CAPIF in Kubernetes has been described in section 4.1

6.1.2 DEPLOYMENT

CAPIF deployment will take place during Trial Networks instantiation by the TNLCM.

6.2 CAPIF DAY 1 OPERATION

6.2.1 CAPIF CONFIGURATION

CCF has been developed using Containers technology. CAPIF configuration is simple as of today, with only two parameters that can be specified when launching CCF:

1. **HOSTNAME:** This parameter allows specifying the URL where NGINX will be publishing CCF services.
2. **MONITORING_STATE:** This parameter allows specifying if the monitoring stack described in section 6.2.4 will be launch along with CCF to collect metrics on how CCF is performing.

CCF provides a script to launch CCF using these parameters. This script is located in /services folder and the script name is run.sh.

In order to launch CCF, the following commands should be typed:

```
cd services/  
  
./run.sh
```

When specifying a URL to start CAPIF, the following command must be used:

```
./run.sh -h HOSTNAME_URL
```

To launch CFF with monitoring enabled, the following command should be used:

```
./run.sh -m true
```

Both parameters can be used simultaneously to specify the URL and enable monitoring:

```
./run.sh -h HOSTNAME_URL -m true
```

These parameters will be configured as part of the CAPIF component in the 6G-SANDBOX Library.

6.2.2 SANITY CHECK

When CCF is running, all services will be running inside Kubernetes. To list the services running, the following docker commands can be used:

```
docker-compose ps --services
```

The following output will be obtained:

access-control-policy

api-invocation-logs

api-invoker-management

api-provider-management

capif-events

capif-routing-info

capif-security

logs

mongo

mongo-express

mongo_register

nginx

published-apis

redis

register

service-apis

vault

In order to facilitate the sanity check and verify that all CCF services are running, CCF provides a script that automates this process:

```
./check\_services\_are\_running.sh
```

When all CCF services are running, the script will return “All services are running” as output.

6.2.3 CAPIF MANAGEMENT

CCF management from command line is very simple. There are scripts to run CCF and to stop CCF. These scripts use docker commands to start or stop all containers that are included in CCF image.

To start CCF the run.sh script must be used as described in section 6.2.1:

```
./run.sh -h HOSTNAME_URL -m true
```

To stop CCF, the stop.sh command must be used as follows:

```
./stop.sh
```

Besides the command line basic operations, 6G-SANDBOX will be using a Backoffice Web tool for management functions. Backoffice Web tool has been described in section 4.2.

6.2.4 CAPIF MONITORING

CAPIF monitoring has been described in section 4.2.5.

6.3 CAPIF DAY 2+ OPERATION

6.3.1 CAPIF UPGRADES

6G-SANDBOX will be using the releases from OpenCAPIF from ETSI once they are published. It is expected that OpenCAPIF will document upgrade procedures when releasing each version. 6G-SANDBOX will follow OpenCAPIF instructions when upgrading versions of OpenCAPIF.

6.3.2 CAPIF TROUBLESHOOTING

Troubleshooting CAPIF will require access to CAPIF Management tool. The admin user doing the troubleshooting will need to use his credentials to log in to the tool:

Figure 46: CAPIF Management tool Login box

After entering credentials, the user will get to the landing page of the tool. This landing page shows a summary of the API Invokers and Providers registered as well as APIs published.

Figure 47: CAPIF Dashboard

From this Dashboard, the admin user can get to the API Invokers and API Providers registered and delete any of them if required.

6.3.2.1 DELETING AN API INVOKER

In order to Delete an API Invoker, the Admin user should go to the Invokers section in the left menu. This section will display the list of registered API Invokers. From the list, the admin user should click in the DELETE button at the right of the API Invoker Identification.

Figure 48: Deleting an API Invoker

6.3.2.2 DELETING AN API PROVIDER

In order to Delete an API Provider, the Admin user should go to the Providers section in the left menu. This section will display the list of registered API Providers. From the list, the admin user should click in the DELETE button at the right of the API Provider information.

Figure 49: Deleting an API Invoker

6.3.2.3 DELETING A PUBLISHED API

In order to Delete a Published API, the Admin user should go to the Providers section in the left menu. This section will display the list of registered API Providers. From the list, the admin user should click in the API Provider that has published the API. After selecting the API Provider, the Provider information will be displayed, including the APIs published by this provider. The APIs listed will have a DELETE button at the right. Clicking the DELETE button the admin user can delete the published API.

Figure 50: Deleting a Published API

6.3.2.4 DELETING A SECURITY CONTEXT

In order to Delete a Security Context, the Admin user should go to the Invokers section in the left menu. This section will display the list of registered API Invokers. From the list, the admin user should click in the API Invoker that has requested the Security Context. After selecting the API Invoker, the Invoker information will be displayed, including the Security Contexts requested by this Invoker. The Security Contexts listed will show the

Authentication Method selected in this security context and will have a DELETE button at the right. Clicking the DELETE button, the admin user can delete the Security Context.

Figure 51: Deleting a Security Context

6.3.2.5 TROUBLESHOOTING WITH LOGS

CAPIF generates Logs for every transaction that takes place in CAPIF Core Function. The Logs have the following structure:

- **Timestamp:** of the event generating the Log entry
- **Level:** assigned to the Log. It can be “INFO”, “DEBUG” and “ERROR”.
- **Logger:** Is the Class reporting the Log.
- **Function:** the Function inside CAPIF generating the log.
- **Line:** line code generating the Log
- **Message:** The message that the Log is generated for.

Some Logs are displayed as an example:

```

{"timestamp": "14/11/2023 09:18:11", "level": "DEBUG", "logger": "__main__", "function": "add_apiinvokerenrolmentdetail", "line": 84, "message": "Invoker inserted in database}
{"timestamp": "14/11/2023 09:18:11", "level": "DEBUG", "logger": "__main__", "function": "add_apiinvokerenrolmentdetail", "line": 85, "message": "Netapp onboarded successfully}
{"timestamp": "14/11/2023 09:18:11", "level": "INFO", "logger": "__main__", "function": "onboarded_invokers_post", "line": 120, "message": "Invoker Created}
{"timestamp": "14/11/2023 09:18:14", "level": "INFO", "logger": "__main__", "function": "onboarded_invokers_post", "line": 117, "message": "Creating Invoker}
{"timestamp": "14/11/2023 09:18:14", "level": "DEBUG", "logger": "__main__", "function": "add_apiinvokerenrolmentdetail", "line": 60, "message": "Creating invoker resource}
{"timestamp": "14/11/2023 09:18:14", "level": "DEBUG", "logger": "__main__", "function": "add_apiinvokerenrolmentdetail", "line": 71, "message": "Signing Certificate}

{"timestamp": "14/11/2023 09:18:14", "level": "DEBUG", "logger": "__main__", "function": "add_apiinvokerenrolmentdetail", "line": 78, "message": {"request_id": '65930ac5-70a1-92ac-7fe7-
b5932cb37733', 'lease_id': '', 'renewable': False, 'lease_duration': 0, 'data': {'ca_chain': ['-----BEGIN CERTIFICATE-----
\nMIIDKDCACgAwIBAgIUImEY0Qbc8Fo+p5UxNUOMy45S/vQwDQYJKoZIhvcNAQEL\nBQAwEDEMGA1UEAxMFY2FwaWYyZmFwYyWwHhcNMjM0MDgzMzAzWWhcNMjM0MDgzMzAzMzYw
MzWjAnMSUwLWYyVGV0QDEExjYXBpZiBjb2RlcmlZGlhdGUgQXV0aG9yaXR5MIIB\nIjANBgkqhkiG9w0BAQEFAAOCAQ8AMIIBCgKCAQEAmoLc+HAOZuQa++dietmMODwZ\njnj+K2IMX9GJMf7c12IXW5ROiodiWY75FD1KpFmniFaPrnPofwKB7kNNS1OyMObjm\n\nM9/0o2aOngPcIUoQilae9sMOSpX6sND9Yw6mmtCMgkWdNd3RIEZ89D1at9pfAh4\n\nfyFu/LBP+zjNpTZf3yEjKnVB8RcKn/HAWHYnmL4qoVplm0hAHQXE4Faf0sqtdkw\n\nQIB9L5goRhaahLaGddakB89HY7fZ7L/gY6TS+rPEX89GBTATTLGA2A/PNvQK/Dc\n\nnjdUwnUP5ahUny1jrPjTjUyW6Mh14QFZY0yE9fkNL6GXTfvARJccAYUEJKG48YdQID\n\nnAQABo2MwYTAOBgNVHQ8BAf8EBAMCAQYwDwYDVR0TAQH/BAUwAwEB/zAdBgNVHQ4E\n\nnFgQU731e5sPUKE4CGrzwjgwnQLH1qnAwHwYDVR0jBBgwFoAUPUGN0CatmNDHn+sL\n\nnugbZ2hWN3TgwDQYJKoZIhvcNAQELBQADggEBAMDFNa48Za7iSkB0doRw+4dwp5p\n\nl\n6GF6XP7yWU4YLQIGCFxVDBPfi3dN72dyJbmOLdofwOnRVnyWa+QPPOhzeBODzd\n\nv\nK2CkQ/mhKz/m8hnUoONbLSA0IFW1ljcoAIAFvzZlw9r7UsAlvVWFKIVj8OXzBL6\n\n\nnMBca0OvaCvCZIIDGWqHWhZonun+iesYXT6b85cgf81KO2kLUpFrPs/72FKhK3gEX\n\n\nnlfPv/QFF9riewFz4qgWnFGec4vDPRKcx+S4g5J8G558MDpkCkn7nD8htuRbsdv1\n\n\n00WZzeERS+ID8DgcVMkPMdBRIbdLxjrlC9zkkb2ObibHZKwI/5pup5k7k=\n\n\n-----END CERTIFICATE-----'}

```

Figure 52: Logs example from the API Invoker

Admin users can check the Logs for troubleshooting and see the information generated by CAPIF. Logs are rotated to avoid filling up the storage allocated to CAPIF. The established rotation policy dictates a maximum limit of 20 log files, each with a maximum size of 100 MB.

7 CONCLUSION

This deliverable begins by describing the concept of the 6G-Library and Trial Network. The former is simply a set of hardware or software components, isolated from other trial networks and accessible to experimenters, while the latter contains all the components that can be added to a Trial Network. The relationship between the two has also been explained to facilitate this deployment. In addition, this document details the process of incorporating objects derived from the development of technological components in WP3 into the 6G-Library, including the tools utilized for the deployment and configuration of these components.

Subsequently, a comprehensive description of CAPIF has been provided as a fundamental element for securely exposing network core APIs to third-party domains and enabling third parties to define and expose their own APIs. The CCF (CAPIF Core Function) has also been described as a crucial element for managing API exposure and consumption. It is highlighted that within a Trial Network, the CCF is treated as an entity within the 6G-Library, with all essential elements provided to facilitate its deployment and activation. Following deployment, it has been demonstrated that this component encompasses not only distinct APIs for each of its services but also features a graphical management tool for interacting with and controlling various functionalities.

Furthermore, the CAPIF Core Function is a mandatory component that all 6G-SANDBOX facilities must have, and it is necessary to deploy at least one CCF to expose APIs from the objects in the 6G-Library. In this way, experimenters can add the CCF to their trial network as another component of the 6G-Library. This document explains the structure of the different repositories used for CAPIF and, in general, the 6G-Library. As a result, experimenters possess comprehensive documentation on CAPIF and other objects in the 6G-Library, facilitating their seamless deployment and utilization.

Finally, considering CAPIF as a software component, the concluding section of this document delineates the approach to managing various updates and upgrades it may undergo in the forthcoming years. This section outlines the lifecycle management structured in a Day 0/Day 1/Day 2+ framework.

REFERENCES

- [1] TS 33.122 Security aspects of Common API Framework (CAPIF) for 3GPP northbound APIs <https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=3420>
- [2] OAuth 2.0 Framework IETF RFC 6749 <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc6749>
- [3] TS 23.222 Common API Framework for 3GPP Northbound APIs <https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=3337>
- [4] MongoDB database <https://www.mongodb.com>
- [5] Hasicorp Vault identity based security <https://www.vaultproject.io>
- [6] REDIS in-memory data store <https://redis.io>
- [7] TS 29.222 Common API Framework for 3GPP Northbound APIs <https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=3450>
- [8] OpenCAPIF from ETSI <https://ocf.etsi.org>

ANNEX 1

Glossary

Term	Description
Facility (or the 6G-SANDBOX facility) (or 6G-Experimentation facility)	The full set of 6G-SANDBOX components that are offered as a pan-European testbed for testing. The testing procedures can be for 6G technology validations and for 6G KPI measurements. The facility is expected to include the implementation of all the components that will be structured around a 6G-SANDBOX reference architecture.
Experimentation platform (or Platform)	An End-to-End platform (a system with integrated Radio Access Network, Network Core, Transport and services) that include 6G-enabled components/features and experimentation services as well as local cloud infrastructure capabilities. Four platforms support the 6G-SANDBOX project, namely the Malaga platform, the Athens Platform, the Berlin platform, and the Oulu platform.
Site (or Platform's Site) (or Experimentation platform's Site)	A location-dependent part of an experimentation platform. The various sites of a platform should be well interconnected and interfaced, but this interconnection and interfacing is not necessarily exposed to platform externals. Example: the Athens platform of 6G-SANDBOX is composed of parts that are located in the COSMOTE premises (i.e., parts that define the COSMOTE site of the platform, e.g., the 5G core) and parts at the NCSR campus (i.e., parts that define the NCSR site of the platform, e.g., the 5G access); these two sites are well-connected with an optical fiber link.
Node	It refers to every physical or virtual component that can be identified individually, i.e., it has specific purpose (provides a kind of service) and it encompass one or multiple technological features. Examples are a 5G-NR antenna, a RIS system, an IoT end-device, a network application, a network function, a set of network functions that compose network core, an experimentation tool, etc.
Trial Networks	Fully configurable, manageable and controllable network which combines digital/virtual and physical nodes and provides services for 6G technology validation and 6G KPI measurements. Instances of Trial Networks might be offered targeting specific network domains and technologies. End-to-end Trial Networks will be offered by the four experimentation platforms that support the 6G-SANDBOX project.
6G Library	To support reusability, openness, and long-term evolution a meaningful set of software components -that will be provided to and/or developed for the 6G-SANDBOX facility - will be packed and offered in a relevant repository (e.g., GitHub) together with the required documentation in order to create an open reference software library, which will not only be under continuous enhancement by the project partners, but it is also meant to serve as an index and sink point for other developments (during and beyond the project lifetime).
6G KPI and KVI repository	To maximize the contribution towards a 6G experimentation ecosystem, all the results of the experimentation processes performed on the 6G-SANDBOX facility will be stored in an open 6G KPI & KVI repository following a common and structured format (based on the SNS JU work in the related WGs) and they will be accessible by other projects/stakeholders, and thus, subject to external analysis.
Technology validation test (or 6G Technology validation)	Tests using the 6G-SANDBOX facility targeting to assess whether a component/node operates and interacts properly, and also provide expected results. The Technology validation tests target the assessment of components/nodes within an overall system. E.g., the tests to validate that the API framework of 6G-SANDBOX is well integrated in the overall testbed.

KPI measurement campaigns (or 6G KPI measurements)	Tests using the 6G-SANDBOX testbed targeting the quantification (selection of values) for well-defined KPIs (e.g., KPIs defined in the 6G-SANDBOX proposal/DoA, or selected ones from the related SNS JU work group).
Architecture (or Reference Architecture)	The main representation of the 6G-SANDBOX facility . It can be provided in various levels of detail (abstractions) or viewpoints (e.g., functional, topology, implementation etc.). A first version of the 6G-SANDBOX Reference Architecture is in the proposal/DoA. Based on the components, the interfaces, the technologies, the tools, and the structure that might be depicted in the Reference Architecture, the development teams should be able to implement the relevant functions, processes, and services.
Physical Infrastructure Layer	The lower layer of the 6G-SANDBOX Reference Architecture . It includes the functions and the components needed for providing end-to-end 6G-enabled connectivity (each of the 4 6G-SANDBOX platforms are included here)
Resource Management Layer	The mid layer of the 6G-SANDBOX Reference Architecture . It manages computational and network resources and forming them as Trial Networks to be offered for experimentation. It may operate in a cross-platform manner / above the local (platform specific) controllers and managers. It may also include functions and components needed for optimizing the Trial Networks, e.g., with AI capabilities and Security guarantees.
Experimentation lifecycle Layer	The upper layer of the 6G-SANDBOX Reference Architecture . It includes the functions and the components needed for controlling the experimentation process and providing the required access to the experimenters.